

THE HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF THE CREATION OF THE POEM "BEOWULF"

Xaydarova Xurshida Rustam qizi¹
Mamajonov Islombek Sardorbekovich²

¹the ministry of higher and secondary
special education of the republic of
uzbekistan samarkand state institute of
foreign languages english faculty ii
206-gruppa xta

²student of the 347th group of
Andijan State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6516959>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th April 2022

Accepted: 25th April 2022

Online: 30th April 2022

KEY WORDS

destruction, Competition, manuscript, resemblance, origin, author, story, Library.

ABSTRACT

We are talking about the history of the United Kingdom and its traditions. This means that the British Isle was subjected to various invasions in the eleventh century. The OROL, on the other hand, was much more comfortable for strangers as it was washed by the warm currents of the Gulf. The southern part of the island was washed away. There would be bloodshed and destruction due to various invasions, but one useful tome was that in each war, people of different nationalities with new worldviews would come in, and thus a new nation would emerge. 250,000 years ago, cave dwellers lived there. Then, in 2000, the invaders of the Iberian Islands, modern-day Spain and Portugal, defended their culture and erected a huge rock in Stonehenge.

Then a new group of Celts emerged from them. The Celts, who came from the East, reached the Aral Sea 600 years ago and then spread throughout Europe. They first cultivated the Bronze and later iron tools. In addition, some Celtic tribes had their own weapons, sometimes fighting each other and building wooden and stone fortresses. But their priests sacrificed in a forest called the Duryids. People living in Britain at that time were called British. Unfortunately, in the century before our era, the Romans conquered Britain. Because at that time the Romans were very smart people in building high bridge buildings. That is why the Romans taught

the British people so much. But by the 4th century, Britain was out in Rome. The Anglo-Saxons were the Progressive people of that time. When they invaded Britain, they invaded and were called runes. The various stories and poems they created about them have been passed down by word of mouth. In addition, folklore flourished at work and in war. There was also a singing group called Bard. They created a variety of memorable songs. The songs they created were about brave people and the courage they showed in battle. Such songs have been passed on to children and then to grandchildren, and have been preserved through writers who

eventually called them ulama. The word writer is derived from the Latin word scribere, meaning to write. Old English poems have also glorified the courage of imaginary or truly brave people. And in order to cultivate a person in the spirit of patriotism.

In addition, the largest work in England is Beowulf. This work won the competition of the most famous English writer. There is a clear example in stories and detective stories from the Middle Ages to the present. There are many works and books in the world but they have a common idea. They have all made a tremendous contribution to the development of the UK. About the epic "Beowulf".

Beowulf, one of the most beautiful poems of the Anglo-Saxons, can be called the foundation of all British poetry. It tells the story of a time long before the Anglo-Saxons came to Britain. It doesn't talk about England but it does talk about the social issues in it. The poem was created by an unknown author over a period of about 700 years. This was about seventy years after Muhammad's death and coincided with the beginning of the great Tang dynasty in China. Three hundred years later, in the year 1000, the manuscript, which has survived to the present day, is said to have been written by an unknown scribe. The poem traces the legendary history of the Anglo-Saxons, and its author may have speculated that he was from the original tribes of the English, Saxons, and Juts, who invaded Britain from the European continent in the fifth century. These people spoke German as written in the poem. The length of the Beowulf is 3182 lines, and the length of the book is about 80 or 90 pages. The story itself is divided into 2 parts: the first part describes

the events that took place in Denmark, where Beowulf, who came to the aid of King Hrotgar, fought the beasts Grendel and Grendel's mother. The second part takes place in southern Sweden, where after the death of King Hygelac and his son Herred, Beowulf reigns in peace and prosperity for 50 years, terrifying the country after having a treasury fund. The slayer had to fight the dragon and return the plundered treasure. Beowulf combines a fairy tale with important historical material. (The kings of Sweden and Denmark actually ruled in the sixth century).

The Beowulf manuscript is housed in the British Museum in London. A non-expert cannot read the original of the work, so it was translated into modern English in the 20th century.

Origin of the poem Beowulf:

Beowulf may have been created as a biography for a king who died in the seventh century, but there is no evidence that the king could have been. The burial rites described in the epic bear great resemblance to the evidence found in Sutton Hoo, but are unknown to form a direct connection between the poem and the burial place.

Poetry can be formed as early as c. At 700, it evolved in many translation processes before it was written. Whoever the original author might be is lost in history.

History of the Beowulf Manuscript:

The only manuscript of Beowulf's poem c. 1000. The handwriting style indicates that it was written by two different people. It is not clear whether the author or writer is embellishing or altering the original story.

The oldest owner of the manuscript is the 16th-century scholar Lawrence Nowell. In the 17th century, it became part of the

Robert Bruce Cotton Collection and is therefore known as Cotton Vitellius A.XV.

Now in the British Library.

In 1731, the manuscript caused irreparable damage to the fire.

The first transcription of the poem was made in 1818 by the Spanish scholar Grimmer Johnson Torkelin. Due to the subsequent fragmentation of the article, Thorkelin's version is highly rated, but its accuracy is being questioned.

In 1845, the manuscript pages were mounted on paper frames, saving them from further damage. It saved the pages, but it also covered some of the letters around the edges.

At last the day came for Beowulf to sail home. Everybody regretted his departure. When Beowulf arrived in his own land, he gave all the treasures he had brought to Hygelac and the people. Beowulf was admired and honoured by everybody. After the death of Hygelac, Beowulf became the king of the Jutes.

For fifty years he ruled his country wisely and well until one day a great disaster befell the happy land: every night there appeared a fire-breathing dragon who came and destroyed the villages. Remembering his glorious youth, Beowulf decided to fight and save his people, but of all his earls only Wiglaf, a brave warrior and heir to the kingdom, had the courage to help him. In a fierce battle the dragon was killed, but his flames burnt Beowulf. Beowulf ordered Wiglaf to take as much treasure as he could carry and give it to the Jutes. In his last hour he thought only of his people, for whose happiness he had sacrificed his life. Beowulf's victory over the monsters symbolized the triumph of a man over the powers of darkness and evil.

Hrothgar, Shild's great-grandson. Hrothgar is well loved by his people and Successful in war. He builds a lavish hall, called Herot (or Heorot), to house his vast Army, and when the hall is finished the Danish soldiers gather under its roof to Celebrate. However, provoked by the singing and carousing of Hrothgar's followers, Grendel, a monster in human shape who lives at the bottom of a nearby swamp, Appears at the hall late one night and kills thirty of the warriors in their sleep. For The next twelve years the fear of Grendel's potential fury casts a shadow over the Lives of the Danes. Hrothgar and his advisers can think of nothing to appease the Monster's anger. Beowulf, prince of the Geats, hears about Hrothgar's troubles, and gathers Fourteen of his bravest warriors, and sets sail from his home in southern Sweden. The Geats are greeted by the members of Hrothgar's court, and Beowulf boasts to The king of his previous successes as a warrior, particularly his success in fighting Sea monsters. Hrothgar welcomes the arrival of the Geats, hoping that Beowulf will Live up to his reputation. During the banquet that follows Beowulf's arrival, Unferth, a Danish soldier, voices his doubts about Beowulf's past Accomplishments, and Beowulf, in turn, accuses Unferth of killing his brothers. Before retiring for the night, Hrothgar promises Beowulf great treasures if he Meets with success against the monster. That night, Grendel appears at Herot, and Beowulf, true to his word, wrestles the monster Bare-handed. He tears off the monster's arm at the Shoulder, but Grendel escapes, only to die soon Afterward at the bottom of the snake-infested Swamp where he and his mother live. The Danish Warriors, who had fled the hall in fear, return singing Songs in praise

of Beowulf's triumph and performing Heroic stories in Beowulf's honour. Hrothgar rewards Beowulf with a great store of treasures and, after Another banquet, the warriors of both the Geats and the Danes retire for the night. Unknown to the warriors, however, Grendel's mother is plotting revenge for Herson's death. She arrives at the hall when all the warriors are sleeping and carries off Esher, Hrothgar's chief adviser. Beowulf, rising to the occasion, offers to dive to The bottom of the lake, find the monster's dwelling place, and destroy her. He and His men follow the monster's tracks to the cliff overlooking the lake where Grendel's mother lives, where they see Esher's bloody head floating on the surface Of the lake. Beowulf prepares for battle and asks Hrothgar to look after his warriors And to send his treasures to his uncle, King Higlac, if he does not return safely. During the ensuing battle, Grendel's mother carries Beowulf down to her Underwater home, but Beowulf finally kills the monster with a magical sword that He finds on the wall of her home. He also finds Grendel's dead body, cuts off the Head, and returns to dry land. The Geat and Danish warriors, waiting expectantly, Celebrate as Beowulf has now purged Denmark of the race of evil monsters. They return to Hrothgar's court, where the Danish king is duly thankful, but Warns Beowulf against the dangers of pride and the fleeting nature of fame and Power. The Danes and Geats prepare a great feast in celebration of the death of The monsters and the next morning the Geats hurry to their boat, anxious to begin The trip home. Beowulf bids farewell to Hrothgar and tells the old king that if the Danes ever again need help he will gladly come to their assistance. Hrothgar Presents

Beowulf with more treasures and they embrace, emotionally, like father And son. Beowulf and the Geats sail home and, after recounting the story of his battles With Grendel and Grendel's mother, Beowulf tells the Geat king Higlac about the Feud between Denmark and their enemies, the Hathobards. He describes the Proposed peace settlement, in which Hrothgar will give his daughter Freaw to Ingeld, King of the Hathobards, but predicts that the peace will not last long.

Beowulf author or authors:

Beowulf contains many pagan and folklore elements, but there are also undisputed Christian themes. This hypocrisy has led some to interpret the epic as the work of several authors. Others see it as a symbolic sign of the transition from Christianity to Christianity in early medieval Britain. The extreme subtlety of the manuscript, the two separate hands that wrote the text, and the complete lack of hints about the identity of the author make a clear decision at its best.

Beowulf story:

Beowulf is the prince of the southern state of the Font, who comes to Denmark to rescue King Hrotgar from a horrible beast called Grendel from Heorot. The protagonist inflicts a deadly wound on an animal that escapes from the hall to die in the morgue. The next night Grendel's mother comes to Hyoro to avenge the seed and kills Hrotgar's men.

Beowulf follows him and kills him, then returns to Heorot, who has received great honor and gifts before returning home.

After the Geats are ruled by peace, Beowulf must meet a dragon that threatens her husband. Unlike previous wars, this confrontation is horrific and deadly. He gave up all his servants except his cousin

Wiglaf, and even if he defeated the dragon, he would not die. He ends his funeral and a screaming poem.

Conclusion

“Beowulf” is the oldest known epic poem written in English, although its date is not known with any certainty (the best estimate being 8th Century CE, and definitely before the early 11th century CE). The author is likewise unknown, and represents a question that has mystified readers for centuries. It is generally thought that the poem was performed orally by memory by the poet or by a “scop” (a travelling entertainer), and was passed down in this way passed down to readers and listeners, or that it was finally written down at the request of a king who wanted to hear it again. Because of the unified structure of the poem, with its interweaving of historical information into the flow of the main narrative, the poem was most likely composed by one person, although there are two distinct parts to the poem and some scholars believe that the sections which take place in Denmark and the sections which take place back in Beowulf’s homeland were written by different authors. It is written in a dialect known as Old English (also referred to as Anglo-Saxon),

A dialect that had become the language of its time by about the early part of the 6th Century CE, in the wake of the occupation of the Romans and the increasing influence of Christianity. Old English is a heavily accented language, so different from modern English as to appear almost unrecognizable, and its poetry is known for its emphasis on alliteration and rhythm. Each line of “Beowulf” is divided into two distinct half-lines (each containing at least four syllables), separated by a pause

and related by the repetition of sounds. Almost no lines in Old English poetry end in rhymes in the conventional sense, but the alliterative quality of the verse gives the poetry its music and rhythm. The poet also makes use of a stylistic device called “kenning”, a method of naming a person or thing by using a phrase that signified a quality of that person or thing (e.g. a warrior might be described as “the helmet-bearing one”). Another characteristic of the poet’s style is his use of litotes, a form of understatement, often with negative overtones, which is intended to create a sense of irony. Most often the characters just deliver speeches to one another, and there are no real conversations as such. However, the story is kept moving quickly by leaping from one event to another. There is some use of historical digressions, similar to the use of flashbacks in modern movies and novels, and this interweaving of events of the present and the past is a major structural device. The poet also sometimes shifts the point of view in the midst of an action in order to offer multiple perspectives (for example, to show the reactions of the warriors who are looking on as an audience in almost every battle). “Beowulf” is part of the tradition of epic poetry that began with the poems of Homer and Virgil, and it deals with the affairs and deeds of brave men, but, like its classical models, it makes no attempt to portray a whole life chronologically from beginning to end. It also functions as a kind of history, blending past, present, and future in a unique, all-encompassing way. It is not just a simple tale about a man who kills monsters and dragons, but rather a large-scale vision of human history. As in the earlier classical epic poems of Greece and Rome, the characters are generally

presented in realistic fashion, but also from time to time as the poet considers they ought to be. Occasionally, the poet breaks his objective tone to offer a moral judgment on one of his characters, although for the most part he lets the actions of the characters speak for themselves. As in the classical tradition of epic poetry, the poem is concerned with

human values and moral choices: the characters are capable of performing acts of great courage, but conversely they are also capable of suffering intensely for their deeds. The poet attempts to some extent to reconcile the "human" and the "heroic" sides of Beowulf's personality.

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